

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN TRAINING FUTURE SPECIALISTS

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Abstract: *the article presents the specific features of methodical competence in the training of future specialists, and the integral and continuous connection of professional, technological and methodical competence in the training of future specialists in the educational process is described. Independent and free thinking, improvement of acquired knowledge is given to learners.*

Key words: *competence, technology, methodical competence, methodical system, form, method, information and communication technologies.*

I. INTRODUCTION.

As in all fields, in the educational system, the results of scientific development, as well as the introduction of modern information and communication technologies, lead to rapid updating of knowledge in various fields of science. Today, when the amount of information is increasing, learners need to use different forms of educational literature in order to quickly acquire new knowledge. The content of the educational literature should provide students with the ability to think independently and freely, to improve the acquired knowledge, to search for new knowledge in various educational literature.

The perspective of our country, the effectiveness of the work in the field of building a democratic society based on the laws of the market economy is inextricably linked with the problem of training competitive specialists, forming a well-rounded generation at the level of developed countries.

II. LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It is necessary to pay special attention to the general professional and methodical preparation of the expected result during the training of future specialists

in educational institutions. Future specialists should be formed on the basis of competencies specified in state educational standards and qualification requirements.

N.A. In Muslimov's literature "Basics of Pedagogical Competence and Creativity", methodical competence is methodologically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correctly defining the forms of educational or educational activity, being able to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, being able to use methods effectively, tools It is given that it consists of successful application.

At the same time, N.L. Stefanova gives the following content to the concept of "educational-methodological system": "it is a model that reflects various components of the educational process, including goals, content, methods and forms, means and planned educational results" [Stefanova N.L. Theoretical foundations of the development of a methodical training system for a teacher of mathematics at a pedagogical university: Dissertation abstract. doc. diss. - SPb., 1996].

T. A. Voronenko in determining the methodical system of education [Voronenko T. A., N.I. Rijova Informatics teaching methodology. Special techniques: A textbook for students. - St. Petersburg: Ros. ped. un-t, 1997] suggests that:

- 1) identifying goals outside the system;
- 2) expanding the set of methodological system elements by adding the following elements:
 - expected results from education;
 - technologies for choosing educational content, methods, forms and tools;
 - technologies for establishing connections between the elements of the methodological system.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The role of highly qualified specialists is extremely important in the reforms carried out in our republic. The role of innovative technologies in higher education institutions in the formation of technological competence of future teachers is

increasing. The use of remote technologies has expanded the possibilities of modern education. Today, it is possible to get an education from anywhere in the world using modern information and communication technologies (ICT). After all, even if traditional education maintains its position, distance learning technologies are becoming popular day by day. The development of the socio-economic policy in accordance with the development of the republic and the market economy requires the improvement of the content of professional education, which meets the requirements of the time and ensures the effectiveness of the processes of training, retraining and upgrading the qualifications of highly qualified pedagogues. This, in turn, created the need to update the content of continuous education, which serves to form the professional competence of specialists, to introduce innovative forms and methods of teaching, modern information and communication technologies into practice.

On this basis, a number of measures are being implemented in higher education institutions today to improve the quality of education, to ensure the coherence and continuity of educational stages. It is known that modernizing the educational process in higher education institutions, developing the technological competence of teachers in improving the quality of the system of training pedagogues, equipping them with modern professional knowledge, qualifications and skills in the field, independent of scientific and technical innovations, creative use and the development of the ability to solve prospective tasks are important requirements. In our country, we have achieved the creation of the base of opportunities necessary for raising a mentally mature, spiritually healthy, harmonious generation.

The main factor in improving the effectiveness of education is the implementation of educational technologies, especially information and communication technologies, the rational use of multimedia resources, the result of which is the growth of the student's ability to know. The advantage of information and communication technologies is that they teach students to think independently, expand their worldview, listen and observe, strive and search, develop thinking, and

work independently. Teacher and student work together. The teacher, as a manager, shows different directions to the student. The student is active in the course of the lesson and thinks independently.

In this, ensuring the interdependence, coherence and continuity of educational stages; introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies for the organization of the educational process in higher education, ensuring the quality of educational and methodological complexes in this regard, constantly improving the literacy of professors and teachers in the use of computers and the Internet in the introduction of pedagogical technologies to go further development of the provision of the educational system with information resources and modern educational literature; it is important to study advanced foreign experiences in these areas. Therefore, in the current period, in order to increase the effectiveness of education, develop the level of technological competence of future specialists, and direct the teaching staff to innovative activities, first of all, the implementation of innovative education and information and communication technologies in the educational process in higher education institutions, assimilation of advanced foreign experiences and targeted orientation were identified as urgent tasks.

In our republic, all links of the educational system are provided with new scientific literature. They are introducing innovations in their activities based on the requirements placed on teachers. In the process of educating the young generation, along with the use of science, technology and advanced experiences, modern pedagogical technologies are effectively used. This process increases teachers' sense of responsibility. The main basis of pedagogical technology depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the student to systematically and cooperatively achieve a guaranteed result based on a clear sequence. The main features of pedagogical technologies are design, implementation and guaranteed result. The main goal of interactive methods is to encourage students to take active action, involve them in the lesson, and teach them to work cooperatively. Such methods include: "Zinema-zina", "Charkhpalak", "Boomerang", "Problem", "Resume", "FSMU", "Fan", "Written discussions", "Venn diagram", "Concept

analysis", There are several methods such as "Dialogue", "Three by four", "Blitz survey" and so on. Currently, with the creation and development of educational materials and the possibility of displaying information on the screen, the use of the achievements achieved in the educational process is becoming widespread. The application of modern information technologies to the educational process creates an opportunity to widely use new educational methods in education along with economic efficiency. Classes are becoming more and more popular in special specialized classrooms, such as classrooms equipped with computers, televisions, and VCRs. It is even interpreted as a separate video method. In particular, the introduction of the computer into the educational process allows the widespread use of the video method, which is able to successfully perform didactic functions. As a result, it is also called complex didactic technology. In this:

- providing students with complete and reliable information on the subject, event, process, activity they are studying;
- increasing the role of visualization in the educational process;
- satisfying the wishes, demands, needs, and interests of students;
- establishing effective communication related to testing the knowledge and skills of the teacher;
- provides an objective report on student learning, full and continuous control.

In the organization of modern education, the pedagogue's use of advanced pedagogical technologies, assimilation of interactive methods, and practical implementation of technical and technological tools are of great importance. In a short period of time, it is necessary to deliver certain theoretical knowledge to students, to create skills and competencies in them in relation to certain activities, as well as to control the activities of learners, to assess the level of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by them. requires high pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process. Innovations in the educational process, advanced pedagogical technologies, news, interactive methods of teaching do not enter the educational process by themselves with orders and instructions from above. This is a process that depends on the activity of the teacher and his motivation.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the educational process based on modern information technologies, it fulfills the tasks of helping the main student to easily use the given complex educational information, creating opportunities for independent educational activities of students. Taking this into account, it is necessary to carry out scientific work on the planning of the educational process and the work of the teacher in the modern education system in a wide range, and this shows its effectiveness.

Today's modern education system requires the pedagogue to activate the influence of the individual relationship between the teacher and the student and the possibilities of modern information technologies. The active use of modern information and telecommunication technologies in the educational process leads to a certain change in the place, role and pedagogical activity of the teacher in the educational process. Currently, the main focus is on creating a model of the educational process based on modern information technologies and research on the problems of creating electronic textbooks and training manuals based on multimedia technologies.

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